

Quantum Memory of Musical Compositions

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Abstract. *The perception and appreciation of beauty in a musical composition appears as being related to the amount of memory and balance between expectation and surprise. In this study, we use a formal computing tool derived from quantum mechanics and adapted to music, to measure the degree of memory of orchestral music, including Liebestod by R. Wagner. We discuss our results and further lines of research.*

Keywords: quantum formalism, memory, novelty

1 Introduction

What is more pleasurable, a soft music, or an unexpected chord which creates tension, lately released into a consonance? In one of his talks at Harvard,¹ Bernstein analyzed the beginning of the *Adagietto* from Mahler's Fifth Symphony, with the initial (and thematic) tension of the dominant, quickly released, and the subsequent equilibrium of tension and relaxation throughout the movement—and the sense of ambiguity is related with the unique beauty of this piece. The affective reactions to harmonic, melodic, rhythmic, and orchestration tricks stimulated the curiosity of scientists. Some recent research focuses on the role of surprise and expectation across different listeners and large databases of musical compositions, including modern songs. The physiological responses of the brain are compared with the verbal replies of listeners, which are in turn compared with the characteristics of the musical pieces [1, 2]. The perception (or, more precisely, the appreciation) of *beauty* is probably related to some sort of balance between surprise and expectation, as in an indeterminacy relation [3]. The problem with most works in this topic, with some noticeable exceptions such as [1], is the lack of hard experimental or empirical evidence to prove the beauty of whole artwork. Instead, we should look for the saliency of basic elements or essential principles - in music, they can be repetition, organization, symmetry, and surprise. Even though the concept of beauty and aesthetic pleasure can vary across listeners and cultures, we nevertheless believe that there is a *universal core* of content that is shared, maybe related to the general way how the brain works, and our biological, natural roots—and we share them with non-human animals [4]. Maybe the seek for beauty is related to survival itself [5]. Maybe it is also related to the formal organization of an artwork. Here, we try to use computational tools to characterize the information content

of a musical artwork, i.e. formal grammars to formalize thematic organization [6].

The topic of beauty in nature and in the arts is vast. Here, we focus on a smaller portion of this field, that is, the balance between expectation and surprise. In particular, we consider the *degree of memory* as an essential element of understandability and appreciability of an artwork which unfolds through time. Memory is related with the sequence of events on time and their similarity. In a musical framework, this is related with patterns of pitches, rhythms, timbres, and loudness. The degree of memory in a musical piece can be computed. The amount of memory in a musical composition has been measured using a criterion developed in physics, and adapting it to music [12]. In this paper, we present a preliminary analysis of memory in musical pieces using a quantum-derived measure of the amount of memory. We compare our empirical judgments on similarity/change inside these pieces with the information that can be recovered from these techniques. The computational advantages introduced by quantum computing can be, and are more often applied to research in music information retrieval [10]; quantum simulators are used to create music [9, 11]; the dichotomy between continuous and discrete, one of the principles of quantum mechanics, can lead to deep investigation in all objects involved in music, from the continuum of pitches to the discreteness of scale tones and chords [8] and the modeling of music-theory concepts in terms of forces [7]. For all these reasons, quantum mechanics and quantum computing can provide new insights for music analysis. Our study is a piece in this picture: how a quantum physics-based criterion can be transferred and adapted to the domain of classical physics, in particular musical applications, helps us investigate these criteria's limitations and advantages, as well as lead to objective measurements of parameters related to our perception.

The article is organized as follows. In Section 2, we present our formal tool of analysis, to quantify the level of novelty and expectation. In Section 3, we apply the tools to the chosen musical compositions, and we comment on the obtained results. In Section 4, we summarize our research and provide some hints for its future developments.

¹<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A705zcQPR0Q>

the software GarageBand (grand piano sound), whose output has then been exported to .wav to enable re-listening, and converted to MIDI commands to be computed by our Max/MSP software. The audio files can be listened here: https://bit.ly/qmmc_1 (first part) and here: https://bit.ly/qmmc_2 (second part). In the following, we will be using the term “memory degree” as a synonym of “non-Markovian degree.”

M_c coefficient	Tristan	Rosalia	improvisation
frequency - start	0.9390	0.9132	0.8850
frequency - duration	0.9950	0.9524	0.8734
frequency - intensity	0.8475	0.9479	0.9390
duration - intensity	0.7722	0.9950	0.8264
start - intensity	0.9259	0.9091	0.8850

Table 1: Non-Markovianity coefficients for each typology of musical matrices, computed for the *Tristan*, *Santa Rosalia*, and a two-part improvisation.

Observing the results reported in Table 1, we notice that the values of thematic memory are higher for *Tristan*, as expected, given the *infinite melody* with the progressive transformation of the material. However, the duration-intensity memory degree is lower for *Tristan*: This information takes into account the loudness change and climax in the second half of the piece, corresponding to a high expressive moment. The variations in intensity are more homogeneously distributed in *Rosalia*, and thus the duration-intensity memory degree shows a higher value. Concerning the improvisation, rhythm, and pitch distribution of the improvisation differs between the first and the second part; thus, the frequency-start memory value is lower than the corresponding degree for *Tristan* and *Rosalia*. The same goes with start-intensity memory degree, as the first part of the improvisation presented ostinato patterns and overall a different organization concerning the second one. Thus, the degree of memory is different. However, there is a key difference between the improvisation short takes and the other considered pieces: the orchestral pieces present a more variegated pitch distribution over time, with multiple lines, and superposed rhythms; these elements contribute to the relative lowering of the memory degree concerning the improvisation. For a numerical comparison, we can consider that, in [12], a value of 0.3 for memory degree was obtained comparing a measure with a quasi-random melodic and a completely different measure, constituted only by a whole note.

Figure 3: *Liebestod* from *Tristan und Isolde*, piano-roll notation.

Figure 4: *Santa Rosalia*, piano-roll notation.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

In this article, we considered a quantum-based quantifier, and applied it to the measurement of thematic memory in orchestral pieces.

The next step of the research will include feedback from listeners. In fact, we can explore the level of concordance between computed memory degrees and qualitative judgments of a large sample of listeners. We could also try to understand if the quantifiers can highlight some information non-retrievable from a professional or non-professional listening. Proper experimental validation of our claims could allow us to deepen the interpretation of the results we obtained, and of the future ones to be obtained.

Further research can investigate the degrees of memory of smaller sections of the pieces, comparing the results we can obtain locally with some salient points present in the score, and some elements noticed by listeners. In this way, we will be able to assess with more precision the effect of memory degree on the perception of musical interest, and on the eliciting of attention and aesthetic pleasure. Global and local non-Markovianity coefficients can help assess the approximated interest, at least concerning the degree of *surprise* and *expectation*. The proposed strategy may even become helpful to deal with the virtually infinite pool of generative music! This could offer quantum composers an opportunity to evaluate the interest of the output musical material without the need for long hours of listening.

Maybe science can help understand why something can be perceived as *beautiful*, and maybe, with the right mapping, and understanding, it can also help create new *beauty* in the world.

Availability of codes

The original code for musical-matrix computation was written by M. Mannone in C, for a chapter of her MSc in theoretical physics (2012). It was then used for the article [12], available as a preprint since 2013, and published in 2022. The code was later ported to Max/MSP by Omar Costa Hamido in 2023 [18], making it more interactive, compatible with regular MIDI files as well as live input, and optimizing the workflow.

After having obtained the musical matrices, we computed the non-Markovianity degrees with MatLab. The technique was the following: `[letter] = readmatrix('`path of the .txt file`'),` for matrices `frequency_start,`

frequency_duration, frequency_intensity, duration_intensity, and start_intensity of each of the parts a musical piece is divided into. We obtain matrices A-B-C-D-E-F-G-H-I-L, following the Italian alphabet. Then, we consider pairs of corresponding matrices, e.g., the frequency_start matrices A and B , for the first and the second part of the piece, respectively. We compute: $AB = abs(A - B)$, $DAB = 0.5 * trace(AB)$. The corresponding non-Markovianity degree was then computed as: $1/(1 + DAB)$.

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